

COMPRESSION BEHAVIOUR OF GRAPHENE FLAKES OF VARIOUS THICKNESSES EMBEDDED IN POLYMER MATRICES

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ABSTRACT

In the present study the mechanical response of embedded graphene flakes into polymer matrices is studied either experimentally or theoretically. 2D and G Raman bands are used as the strain sensors, while compressive strain is applied by means of a four point-bending apparatus. It is found that the flakes buckle when a critical strain is reached. A single layer can sustain compressive strains strain up to -0.6% independent of the flake dimensions, while thicker flakes fails at significantly lower strain values. Molecular dynamic simulations, DFT analysis and an analytical approach based on Winkler's are used to model the failure mechanism in single layer graphene under compression. These approaches reveal that the failure is governed by the adhesion between the graphene and the polymer. The molecular dynamics simulations revealed that the form of failure of the embedded graphene is multiple buckling. These simulations agree well with the analytical approach of Winkler's model and confirmed the hypothesis of the buckling form of failure. Also, the buckling wavelength and the amplitude calculated from Winkler's model are in good agreement with the nanoscale simulations. Our results have significant implications for the design of graphene nanocomposites.

1 INTRODUCTION

The mechanical behavior of graphene sheets embedded in polymer matrix under compressive loadings was examined experimentally using Raman spectroscopy. Samples with different dimension ratios were investigated. Using a four-point-bending frame the samples were compressed up to -1% of strain. The measurements were performed at the center of the graphene flakes with a strain step of 0.05%. Raman spectra have been measured at 785 nm using a MicroRaman (InVia Reflex, Renshaw, UK) spectrograph, monitoring the profiles of 2D peak. By monitoring the Raman shift of the 2D peak position vs strain a non linear behavior was observed. The region of small strains can be captured by second order polynomial curves. The critical strain to failure was estimated at the maximum of the above polynomial fitting curve. At the failure point graphene flakes exhibit a multiple rippling form that is mainly affected by the degree of the graphene-polymer interaction. In the case of an embedded graphene sheet the ripples cannot be optically observed due to the intervening PMMA layer. Thus, molecular dynamic simulations were performed and the results confirmed the form of buckling failure. Also simply supported graphene flakes under compression exhibit multiple wrinkling.

Simultaneously, an analytical approach of Winkler type is used to simulate the interaction between graphene and the polymer matrix. Within the framework of continuum mechanics, Winkler's theory models the film–foundation interaction through linear elastic springs. Using energetical arguments we produced the equations for the critical strain of buckling and have estimated the wave form, half-wavelength and amplitude of the buckling mode.

Graphene flakes consisting of one to three layers were examined. The monolayers failed at compressive strain of -0.6%, bilayers at -0.25% and trilayer at -0.20%. The critical strain to buckling was found to be independent of the flake's dimensions for all thicknesses.

2 DISCUSSION

Monolayer graphene

In previous studies [1, 2] single layer graphenes under compression were examined using the technique of the cantilever beam. As shown in these studies, the critical strain to failure can be estimated by monitoring the shift of the 2D Raman band with the applied strain. Further experiments were carried out using a four point bending technique. Several graphene samples of almost rectangular geometry with varying dimensions ratio were tested. In **table 1** the data and the results of the previous studies and the newer are presented.

As it seen in figure 1a, the behaviour is non linear and can be capture by a second order polynomial curve. The critical strain to failure corresponds to the point that the slope of the curve is zero. The value of the slope at zero strain of this curve is a crucial parameter for the design of graphene polymer nanocomposites, because it reflects the efficiency of the stress transfer from the polymer to the graphene. From the experimental results, it is observed that graphene sheets with length of about 4 μm , have smaller slope from these with larger length. The mean value for the slope from the flakes with sufficient transfer length is $60 \text{ cm}^{-1}/\%$ ⁸. Thus, in order to obtain the actual strain for graphene with small length the following formula is proposed (figure 1b)⁸:

$$\varepsilon_{\text{graphene}} = \varepsilon_{\text{applied}} \left(\frac{\left(\frac{\partial \Delta \nu}{\partial \varepsilon} \right)_{\text{measured}}}{\left(\frac{\partial \Delta \nu}{\partial \varepsilon} \right)_{\text{maximum}} \Big|_{T, \varepsilon=0}} \right) \quad \text{or} \quad \varepsilon_{\text{graphene}} (\%) = \frac{\varepsilon_{\text{applied}} (\%)}{|60|} \left(\frac{\partial \Delta \nu}{\partial \varepsilon} \right)_{\text{measured}, \varepsilon=0} \quad (1)$$

Figure 1. (a) Typical curve of Raman wavenumber of the 2D peak versus applied strain for a flake of length of $30 \mu\text{m}$ and width $6 \mu\text{m}$ (b) dependence of the 2D Raman peak on the strain for the flake with $l=4 \mu\text{m}$ and $w=21 \mu\text{m}$. The open circles correspond to the applied strain of the beam and the solid circles represent the corrected strain values in accordance to eqn 1. The black (dark) and blue (light) lines are second order polynomial fitted curves. The black line is described by the equation $Pos2D_{\text{black}} = 2595.3 - 38.0\varepsilon - 23.9\varepsilon^2$, and the blue line is a rescaling to a slope of $60 \text{ cm}^{-1}/\%$ [8].

Another significant finding is that the critical strain to failure is not affected by the size of the graphene. From the experimental results a mean value of $-0.6 \pm 0.11 \%$ was obtained for the critical strain. Considering the monoatomic thickness of single layer graphene, this is a high value of compressive strain that graphene can sustain, making it a sufficient filler in polymer nanocomposites.

Analytical

The problem is treated analytically with the well known model of Winkler's. The interaction between graphene and the polymer is considered as linear elastic springs which are described by the Winkler's modulus. Winkler's modulus represents the stiffness of the springs with units N/m³. Starting from the energy balance [3] of a system that consists of a plate embedded in an elastic foundation, a formula for calculating the critical strain to buckling as well as the form of instability is obtained. The energy balance of this system is⁸:

$$E = U_b + U_f - T \quad (2)$$

where E is the total energy of the system, U_b is the plate bending energy, U_f is the additional energy from the linear springs between the plate and the foundation that resist to the out-of-plane deformation of the plate, and T is the axial compression energy released by the flake buckling. The corresponding expressions for the terms of eq3 are given by:

$$U_b = \frac{D}{2} \int_A \left\{ \left(\frac{\partial u^2}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial u^2}{\partial y^2} \right)^2 - 2(1-\nu) \left[\frac{\partial u^2}{\partial x^2} \frac{\partial u^2}{\partial y^2} - \left(\frac{\partial u^2}{\partial x \partial y} \right) \right] \right\} dA \quad (3)$$

$$U_f = \frac{K_w}{2} \int_A u^2 dA \quad (4)$$

$$T = \frac{1}{2} \int_A N_x \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} \right)^2 dA \quad (5)$$

Where N_x is the compressive force per unit length applied in x-direction, D is the flexural rigidity and ν is the Poisson's ratio of the plate and K_w is the Winkler modulus.

The assumption that the embedded flake buckles is made, and thus the form of solution of the function $u(x,y)$ of the previous equations is taken as:

$$u(x, y) = \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} u_{mn} \sin\left(\frac{m\pi x}{l}\right) \sin\left(\frac{n\pi y}{w}\right) \quad (6)$$

Where m, n are the half-waves of the buckling mode in the x and y directions, respectively. By inserting the expression of $u(x,y)$ to the energy expressions and after some calculations the following equation for the critical strain to buckling of an embedded plate is:

$$\varepsilon_{cr} = \pi^2 \frac{D}{C} \frac{k}{w^2} + \frac{l^2}{\pi^2 C} \left(\frac{K_w}{m^2} \right) \quad (7)$$

In the above relation C is the tension rigidity of the plate which has been found to be 340 Nm² for graphene [4] while the Euler geometric term k is defined as follows:

$$k = \left(\frac{mw}{l} + \frac{l}{mw} \right)^2 \quad (8)$$

m is the number of half waves that the plate buckles at the initiation of instability. It can be obtained by energy minimization of equation 2, after the calculation we have:

$$m^2(m+1)^2 = \frac{l^4}{w^4} + \frac{l^4 K_w}{\pi^4 D} \quad (9)$$

In our problem, the Winkler modulus is unknown. Considering the critical strain obtained from the experimental results, a system of three equations 7-9 with two unknown parameters, the Winkler's modulus and the number of half waves is obtained. Thus, we solve this system of equations and the obtained results are presented in table 1. The problem of estimating Winkler's modulus is examined in the next section using DFT calculations. The mean value for Winkler's modulus is 6.7 GPa/nm . Finally, since the number of half waves that the flake buckles is known, the buckling wavelength can be estimated by dividing the final length of the flake with the number of half waves. Thus:

$$\lambda = \frac{l(1 - \varepsilon_{cr})}{m} \quad (10)$$

The values for the buckling wave length are of the order of 1-2 nm. This value is about three orders of magnitude than the wave length for buckling of a free standing graphene, without the presence of the polymer (figure 2a,b). Analogous phenomena have been observed for embedded rods in soft matrices [5].

Figure 2. (a) An embedded graphene exhibits multiple rippling under compression with small wavelength. (b) A free standing graphene buckling with orders of magnitude larger wavelength without the presence of the polymer [8].

Bilayer and trilayer graphene

In figure 3 the pos(2D) vs strain is presented for bilayer and trilayer graphene flakes respectively.

The 2D peak strain rates for compressive strains of up to the critical strain were found as -55 and -51 $\text{cm}^{-1}/\%$ for bi and trilayer graphenes, respectively (fig.3). Moreover, the critical buckling strains were found to be -0.25% and -0.22% for bi- and trilayer respectively. These values are readily lower than the -0.60% for a monolayer. A similar result has been reported by us [9] for a trilayer graphene under compression but at an inadequate flake/polymer interface. However, in this work the 2D peak strain rates are comparable with that of single layer graphene at least within this short range of the compressive strains (fig. 1&3). Provided that the 2D peak strain rate can be used to measure the quality of the flake/ polymer interface [10, 11], the studied flakes were under similar shear stress field during compression. Thus, the decrease of the critical buckling strain when the flake thickness increases cannot be attributed to the relatively bad quality of graphene/polymer interface. Critical transfer length effects are not considered here since the length along the strain axis of the examined flakes were large enough to ensure effective strain transfer.

In theory, few layer graphene exhibits three orders of magnitude greater bending stiffness than single layer graphene and one would expect a higher critical buckling strain. When the polymer matrix is deformed, stress is transferred by interfacial stress transfer to the two outer graphene layers. Stress transfer to the inner layer can only take place by shear from the two outer layers. As has been reported previously, the weakest interface is that between the inner graphene layers which in graphite fail at a shear stress of only 30 kPa[10]. For comparison, the shear stress for interfacial stress transfer between the graphene and the polymer is of the order of 1 MPa for model monolayer graphene composites [11]. It is therefore possible that internal shear between the mid and external layers is also present that should lead to premature cohesive failure due to the weakness of the van der Waals forces that bond the layers together.

Figure 3. Experimental results for a (a) bilayer and (b) trilayer graphene fully embedded in polymer under compression.

3 CONCLUSIONS

Graphene membranes of various thicknesses were examined experimentally using Raman spectroscopy and analytically by employing Winkler's model. It was found that single and few layer graphene fail with buckling. The critical strain to buckling was found to be independent of the flake's dimensions in all cases but strongly dependent on flake thickness; critical strain decreases as the number of layers of the flakes increases.

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References

- [1]. Frank, O.; Tsoukleri, G.; Parthenios, J.; Papagelis, K.; Riaz, I.; Jalil, R.; Novoselov, K. S.; Galiotis, C., Compression Behavior of Single-Layer Graphenes. *Acs Nano*, 4 (6), 3131-3138, 2010.
- [2]. Tsoukleri, G.; Parthenios, J.; Papagelis, K.; Jalil, R.; Ferrari, A. C.; Geim, A. K.; Novoselov, K. S.; Galiotis, C., Subjecting a Graphene Monolayer to Tension and Compression. *Small*, 5 (21), 2397-2402, 2009.
- [3]. Timoshenko, S., *Theory of elastic stability*. 2d ed.; McGraw-Hill: New York, p 541, 1961.
- [4]. Lee, C.; Wei, X. D.; Kysar, J. W.; Hone, J., Measurement of the elastic properties and intrinsic strength of monolayer graphene. *Science*, 321 (5887), 385-388, 2008.
- [5]. Brangwynne, C. P.; MacKintosh, F. C.; Kumar, S.; Geisse, N. A.; Talbot, J.; Mahadevan, L.; Parker, K. K.; Ingber, D. E.; Weitz, D. A., Microtubules can bear enhanced compressive loads in living cells because of lateral reinforcement. *J Cell Biol*, 173 (5), 733-741, 2006.
- [6]. Li, Q., Lee, C., Carpick, R.W., Hone, J., Substrate effect on thicknessdependent friction on graphene, *Physica Status Solidi (B)*, 247 (11-12), pp. 2909-2914, 2010.
- [7]. He, Y., Chen, W.F., Yu, W.B., Ouyang, G., Yang, G.W., Anomalous interface adhesion of graphene membranes, *Sci. Rep.* 3, 2660, 2013
- [8]. Androulidakis, C., Koukaras, E.N., Frank, O., G. Tsoukleri, D. Sfyris, J. Parthenios, N, Pugno K. Papagelis, , Novoselov, K.S., Galiotis, C., Failure processes in embedded monolayer graphene under axial compression, 4, 5271, 2014.
- [9]. G Tsoukleri et al, Embedded trilayer graphene flakes under tensile and compressive loading, *2D Mater.* 2 024009 (2015)
- [10]. L. Gong et al., Reversible Loss of Bernal Stacking during the Deformation of Few-Layer Graphene in Nanocomposites, *ACS Nano* 7, p. 7287, (2013).
- [11]. G. Anagnostopoulos, C. Androulidakis, E.N. Koukaras, G. Tsoukleri, I. Polyzos, J. Parthenios, K. Papagelis, C. Galiotis, Stress transfer mechanisms at the submicron level for graphene/polymer systems *ACS Applied Materials and Interfaces*, 7 (7): 4216-4223 (2015)